

SURFACE TREATMENTS FOR BONDING OF COMPOSITES

Durability of vacuum infused composite-composite and composite-steel joints for marine applications

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturers of composite structures are always looking for new jointing techniques to reduce costs and comply with legislations on health and environmental issues. The Centre of Lightweight Structures TUD-TNO (CLS) has been doing research on surface treatments for bonding panels of GFRP composites on steel and on other GFRP composite panels for application at shipyards.

Composite-steel joint

Composite-steel joints can often be found in navy ships, where composite panels are bonded to steel surfaces. For these joints corrosion of the steel substrate plays an important role in the long-term behavior of the joint, especially in marine applications where the joint will be exposed to a large range of temperatures and a salt environment. The standard surface preparation for the steel prior to bonding is cleaning, sanding/grit blasting and priming, although primers are not always used. Cleaning is usually done with a solvent.

The research is focused on comparing different cleaners (for example solvents, water/citrus-based and UV cleaning) and different primers. After surface preparation of the steel, the joint is made by infusing the laminate on top of the steel: the infusion resin also provides the adhesion function. Research on the steel-composite joint is performed on both standard and aged (thermal cycle and salt-spray) specimens. The specimens are tested by the climbing drum peel method to compare the surface treatment variants.

Composite-composite joint

The standard surface preparation for adhesively bonded joints is cleaning, sanding and cleaning. Cleaning is usually done with a solvent. This surface treatment is labor intensive, unpleasant if not harmful for personnel and environmentally unfriendly. In addition it is known that this procedure results in varying quality depending on contamination, condition/situation of application and skill. As such this is an area of concern for most composite manufacturers, especially shipyards. Common manufacturing methods at shipyards are hand lay-up and vacuum infusion. One improvement and frequently used surface preparation method applied at vacuum infusing shipyards is covering the bonding area (during infusion of the panel) with peel ply. Peel ply is a woven material on which certain release agents have been applied for the ease of removing the fabric. The peel ply is kept on the bond area until the panels are bonded. After removing the peel ply a well-determined surface quality exists. However, a certain amount of release agent of the peel ply is left on the bond surface and can have a negative effect on the bond strength.

The research focuses on two subjects: 1) finding a cover ply that after removal provides a chemically fresh surface suitable for bonding and 2) using peel ply and develop a way to easily remove the remaining release agent from the surface. Climbing drum peel tests are performed to compare the surface treatment variants. First results indicate that the fiber-matrix interface has a large influence on the peel strength.

KEYWORDS: Adhesive bonding; surface treatment; resin infusion; durability

1. INTRODUCTION

Structural joints are always important design issues, especially when two different materials are connected. Modern structures (aerospace, automotive, building) often combine different materials (hybrid solutions) to make optimum use of their respective advantages. One of the critical aspects of joints is the surface treatment that is applied on the adherents prior to bonding. A research program was started within the EUCLID (EUropean Cooperation for the Long term In Defense) framework to find practical solutions for surface preparation of both steel and GFRP in order to obtain well-performing bonded composite-composite and composite-steel joints. Field of application is shipbuilding, where composites are increasingly being used in structural parts of navy vessels.

This paper describes a part of the work performed in the EUCLID RTP3.21 project on surface treatments. Section 2 gives a description of the applied mechanical test method. This method was used for both the composite-steel and composite-composite joints. The test programs and test sample manufacturing were different though, and therefore these aspects of the research are described separately in two different sections. Section 3 covers the composite-composite joints, while section 4 takes care of the composite-steel joints. Finally, in section 5 the results of the test program (of both joint types) are summarized in a number of conclusions.

2. TEST METHOD

To discriminate the effects of the different surface treatments, a test method had to be selected. In general, bonded joints in structures are loaded in shear or peel (figure 1). Bonded joints are very sensitive to peel stresses and this type of loading must be avoided as much as possible in structural designs. Shear test values are mostly used as reference values creating structural designs. In most cases however, peel loads will occur locally and can therefore not be neglected.

Figure 1a: Shear load on adhesive joint

Figure 1b: Peel load on adhesive joint

As this initial part of the research program was focused on finding comparative results between a selected baseline treatment and alternative treatments rather than obtaining design values, a peel test was chosen. The applied test method is the “climbing drum peel” as described in ASTM standard D1781 (ref. [6]). In this test, a relatively flexible adherend is peeled around a circular drum from a rigid adherend, see figure 2. The tests were performed on a Zwick BZ1-MM14550.ZW02 20kN testing machine in the Structures and Materials Laboratory of the Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology.

Before starting the actual test, the force was set to zero before the specimen with climbing drum was attached. The average value measured during the peel test therefore consists of the actual force required to peel off the top layer, the weight of the climbing drum and also the roll-up resistance of the top layer that is bent around the drum. To be able to compare only the peel forces, single top layers were tested to determine its roll up resistance. A typical test curve is shown in figure 3.

Figure 2: Climbing drum peel test

Figure 3: Typical test curve for the climbing drum peel tests as performed in this research program

The calculation method described in the ASTM standard results in an average peel torque, influenced by the dimensions of the test drum. Because all samples were tested with the same climbing drum and the results are only used to discriminate the effects of the different surface treatments, not the peel torque is determined but the component of the force required for the peeling process.

$$F = \frac{F_p - F_0}{w} = \frac{F_p - F_{drum} - F_{lam}}{w}$$

T = Average peel torque [mm Kg/mm]

r_0 = Radius of flange including half thickness of the loading strap [mm]

r_i = Radius of the drum plus half thickness of the adherend being peeled [mm]

F_p = Average load required to bend and peel adherend plus the load required to overcome the resisting torque [N]

F_0 = Load required to overcome the resisting torque including the roll up resistance of the top layer [N]

F_{drum} = Load measured when drum is attached to specimen [N]

F_{lam} = Roll up resistance of the top layer laminate [N]

w = Width of specimen [mm]

Peel failure can occur at the interfaces between the different layers or by cohesive failure within one layer. The layers and interfaces of the composite-steel and composite-composite joints are schematically drawn in figure 4. For the composite-composite joint, failure is expected at interface 2 between the top layer resin and the base layer resin (as this is the actual location of the bond).

Figure 4: Layers and interfaces (1-4) of the joints

3. COMPOSITE-COMPOSITE JOINTS

This part of the research program focused on “secondary bonding” of composites. Different treatments were applied on a thick base panel of cured glass fiber reinforced composite before an additional layer of composite is applied on top of this panel by vacuum infusion. No separate adhesive system was tested. Also the influence of the resin and peel ply was examined. The complete program comprised more variables, but these are not within the scope of this paper.

3.1. MATERIALS

Using one type of reinforcement, a variation of resins and peel plies was used in the test program. An overview of these materials and a short description is given in table 1.

Material	Description
<i>Reinforcement</i>	
Chomarat 800 S4	Satin weave, E-glass, warp 390 g/m ² , weft 390 g/m ² , finish 111A
<i>Resins</i>	
Dow Derakane 411-C-50	Epoxy based vinyl ester
Reichhold Norpol Dion 9500-510	Rubber modified epoxy based vinyl ester
Lonza Distitron VE 100SC	Bisphenol-A epoxy based vinyl ester
Reichhold PD 6088	DCPD polyester
Bakelite Rutapox VE 4908	Epoxy
<i>Peel plies</i>	
Stitch ply A	Nylon fabric, without release agent
Bleeder lease A	Nylon fabric, with silicone release
Release ease 234 TFP	Glass fabric, with Teflon (PTFE) coating

Table 1: Overview materials for composite-composite joints

3.2. TEST SAMPLE MANUFACTURE

Vacuum infusion was applied as processing technology to make both the base panels and the top layer (over-laminate). Vacuum infusion is a low-cost derivative of Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) - and therefore a closed mould technology – where dry reinforcement is placed in a semi-rigid mould. The mould is subsequently closed with a foil and vacuum is applied in the product cavity. Subsequently, the reinforcement is impregnated by infusion of the resin, making use of the pressure difference between the product cavity (vacuum) and the resin (ambient). To improve the distribution of the resin over the reinforcement, a flow fabric can be used on appropriate locations on top of the reinforcement. Between the flow fabric and the reinforcement a peel ply must be placed to be able to remove the flow fabric after cure. More information on vacuum infusion is published by Hoebergen and Holmberg (ref. [3]).

Before starting the pre-treatment on one side of the base panel, the panel must be cured. The standard cure (after completing the infusion) consists of the following steps:

1. Cure at room temperature for 16 hours
2. Post cure for 6 hours at 60°

This cure cycle was followed by the surface pre-treatment within two hours. The standard pre-treatment of the base panel consists of the following steps:

1. Removing the peel ply
2. Cleaning the surface with IPA (Isopropylalcohol)
3. Sanding (paper grit 100) until 50% of the peel ply print left on the surface is removed
4. Cleaning the surface again with IPA

After infusion of the top layer, all panels were cured for 16 hours at room temperature, followed by a post cure at 60°C for 6 hours. Test specimens were cut from the panels after completion of the cure cycle.

3.3. TEST PROGRAM

Three groups of test samples were tested to examine the influence of the type of resin, surface treatment, state of cure and peel ply on the secondary bond. An overview of the groups is given in table 2. A description of each group follows below.

Group 1:

In this group five resins and three different pre-treatment procedures were tested: infusion at once (no actual secondary bonding, but infusing a single composite panel), no pre-treatment and standard pre-treatment (see section 3.2). “No pre-treatment” means that the steps 1 and 2 of the standard pre-treatment are applied, but the additional sanding and cleaning steps are not. Injection at once is expected to give the best bond.

Group 2:

In this group the influence of the state of cure of the base laminate before infusing the top layer is tested for four resins. The top layer was infused after standard cure (see section 3.2), partly cure and over cure of the base panel. These two cure variant (after infusion of the base laminate is completed) consist of the following steps:

Partly cure: - Cure at room temperature for 24 hours (no post cure of the base panel)

Over cure: - Cure at room temperature for 16 hours
- Post cure at 60°C for 30 hours

Group 3:

Finally, the effect of using different peel plies for the infusion of the base panel is examined. For secondary bonding it is expected that peel plies with release coatings have a negative influence on the bonding strength.

Nr	Resin	Surface character	Base laminate cure	Solvent wipe	Base laminate preparation	Final treatment
GROUP 1						
2	Dow Derakane 411	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	-	(inj at once)	-
4				IPA	None	None
3				IPA	Standard	IPA
111	Norpol Dion 9500	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	-	(inj at once)	-
112				IPA	None	None
113				IPA	Standard	IPA
71	Bakelite Rütapox 4908	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	-	(inj at once)	-
72				IPA	None	None
73				IPA	Standard	IPA
51	Lonza VE100	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	-	(inj at once)	-
52				IPA	Standard	IPA
61	Reichhold PD6088	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	-	(inj at once)	-
62				IPA	Standard	IPA
GROUP 2						
3	Dow Derakane 411	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	IPA	Standard	IPA
41			Partly cure			
42			Over cure			
113	Norpol Dion 9500	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	IPA	Standard	IPA
114			Partly cure			
115			Over cure			
52	Lonza VE100	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	IPA	Standard	IPA
53			Partly cure			
54			Over cure			
62	Reichhold PD6088	Peel ply, no release coating	Standard	IPA	Standard	IPA
63			Partly cure			
64			Over cure			
GROUP 3						
4	Dow Derakane 411	Stitch A	Standard	IPA	None	None
21		Bleeder A				
22		234 TFP				

Table 2: Test matrix of the composite-composite joints

3.4. RESULTS

Group 1 (figure 5a):

Comparing the results of the five different resins with each other reveals that the epoxy and the Lonza vinyl ester give similar peel strengths, whereas the DCPD polyester is dramatically lower. The two other vinyl esters are somewhere in the middle. Looking at the differences in surface treatments it can

Figure 5a: Results peel tests group 1

Figure 5b: Results peel tests group 2

Figure 5c: Results peel tests group 3

surprisingly be seen that direct infusion on a peel ply surface (no treatment) is not worse than infusion at once. The standard procedure is slightly lower, but gives almost equal results.

All samples show failure in between the top layer resin and top layer reinforcement (see also figure 4), which indicates that the resin-matrix interface in the composite is the weakest link instead of the secondary bond. Only for some of the standard procedure samples some resin seems to be left on the top layer reinforcement at some spots.

Group 2 (figure 5b):

Partly curing the base laminate before infusion of the top layer gives the best results for the three vinyl esters. The results for the over cured panels are about 10% lower and the standard cure is in the middle. The polyester does not show any sensitivity to cure variations, but its peel strength is again much lower than the vinyl esters.

Like in the group 1 experiments, the failure seems to happen between the top layer resin and the top layer reinforcement.

Group 3 (figure 5c):

The effect of the variation in peel plies is very clear. A peel ply with a release coating apparently leaves part of the coating on the base panel after removing the peel ply. As a result, the peel strength reduces dramatically.

For both coated peel plies the failure is completely between the base panel resin and the top layer resin: the top layer is still completely covered with resin after the test.

4. COMPOSITE-STEEL JOINTS

This section describes the work performed on the composite-steel joints. Two different joints were tested: laminated joints that are created during the impregnation of the composite on top of the steel (thus using the resin both as matrix material for the composite and as the adhesive: “over-laminate”) and joints using a separate adhesive system. The baseline treatment for the laminated joint consists of only two steps: cleaning the steel with acetone and grit blasting. The over-laminate is made by applying vacuum infusion technology. Objectives of this part of the research were to find an applicable surface treatment of steel and compare different primer systems. Also, the performance of joints using a pre-selected adhesive system had to be tested. Both non-aged and aged samples were tested. Finally some alternative cleaners were compared with contact measurement on cleaned steel, but this part of the program is not discussed in this paper.

4.1. MATERIALS

In table 3 an overview is given of the materials that were used in the composite-steel joint test program.

Material	Description
<i>Base panel</i>	
Steel 52-3	2 mm thickness
<i>Top layer</i>	
Reichhold Norpol Dion 9500-510	Rubber modified epoxy based vinyl ester
Devold AMT DBL 800-E10-H	Triaxial (0°/+45°/-45°) 800 g/m ² E-glass knitted fabric
<i>Abrasive medium</i>	
Chilled iron grit	Angular shape, grain size G17
<i>Primers</i>	
Edilon U90WB	2-component epoxy based primer
Jotun Penguard Special	2-component epoxy based primer
Sika Icosit EG1	2-component epoxy based primer
<i>Adhesive</i>	
Crestomer 1152PA	Unsaturated urethane acrylate based adhesive, accelerated with 2% Butanox M50
<i>Coating</i>	
Sigma Universal Primer	First layers to be applied (brushing, 2 layers)
Sigma CM Miocoat	Top layers to be applied (brushing, 2 layers)

Table 3: Overview materials for composite-composite joints

4.2. TEST SAMPLE MANUFACTURE

In all cases, the steel panels had the following standard surface treatment:

1. Cleaning with a clean cloth and acetone
2. Grit-blasting
3. Cut the panels to the required test sample size (250x25mm)
4. Cleaning with a vacuum cleaner to remove any present dust
5. If necessary (almost never) cleaning with a clean cloth and acetone of greasy spots

Laminated joints:

After finishing the standard treatment as described above, the next step was applied. This was either an additional cleaning step with UV Ozone light, brushing a layer of primer or infusion of the composite, see also section 4.3. The time between grit blasting and the following step was kept as short as possible (maximum two hours). After curing of the primer (if present) according to the specifications of the supplier, the primed surface was sanded (paper grit 60), followed by cleaning with a clean cloth and acetone. Subsequently, the steel strips were placed on a flat mould and the dry reinforcement was placed on top of the strips with the 0°-fiber direction side facing the steel. After infusion of the resin (figure 6), the panel was cured overnight at room temperature followed by a post-cure of 8 hours at 60°C. After the post-cure, the samples were cut to the required size.

Joints with separate adhesive:

Preparation of the steel adherends is similar to the standard method described above. The composite adherend was made separately by vacuum infusion with the +/-45° fiber direction side facing the mold to avoid contamination of the 0° side by release agent of the mold. After infusion, the composite was cured overnight at room temperature but not post-cured yet. The steel strips were placed on a flat mold and an excess amount of the Crestomer adhesive was put on top of the steel. The composite adherend was placed on top of the adhesive and the adhesive was distributed by careful pressing on top of the composite, thereby pushing the excess of adhesive and voids to the sides and away from the locations of the test samples and leaving an adhesive layer of approximately 1 mm thickness on the samples. The joint was cured at room temperature overnight, followed by a post-cure of 8 hours at 60°C. Finally, the specimens were cut to the required size.

Coating:

In stage 2 of the test program, a number of specimens were protected by a coating. This coating consisted of two parts: a primer (Sigma Universal Primer) and a top coating (Sigma CM Miocoat). Both parts were applied by brushing: two layers of each part were painted on the specimens (while following the application directions as described in the specifications of the supplier).

Figure 6: Three stages of the vacuum infusion process applied during test sample manufacture:
 1) positioning the steel samples on the flat aluminum mould with dummy strips in-between
 2) the vacuum is applied after having placed the dry reinforcement, peel-ply and feeder material on top of the samples and
 3) infusion of the resin and impregnation of the reinforcement.

4.3. TEST PROGRAM

The test program consisted of two stages. The test matrix for both stages is shown below in table 4, followed by a description of each stage.

Sample type	Cleaning		Grit-blasting	Priming				Cure/Post-Cure of resin primer prior to laminating	Separate adhesive (Crestomer 1152PA)	Aging tests (stage 2)
	Acetone	UV		Resin (Norpol Dion 9500-510)	Edilon U90WB	Jotun Penguard Special	Sika Icosit EG1			
VE-0 (Baseline)	X		X							
VE-UV	X	X	X							
VE-SotaA	X		X	X					X	
VE-SotaB	X		X	X					X	
VE-Edilon	X		X		X				X	
VE-Jotun	X		X			X			X	
VE-Sika	X		X				X		X	
VE-Cresto	X		X					X	X	
VE-CrestoJotun	X		X			X		X	X	

Table 4: Test matrix of the test program.

Supported by the conclusion of Harris and Beevers (ref. [2]) that the resulting adhesion strength is not very much influenced by the grit-size, it was decided to include only one abrasive medium in the test program. This abrasive grit was used on all sample types.

The baseline sample (VE-0) has no other treatment than the standard treatment described in section 4.2. This standard treatment is followed by an additional cleaning step with UV-Ozone light for 15 minutes for sample type VE-UV. Priming was performed for five different sample types, including two (SotaA and SotaB) where the composite infusion resin was used as the primer. For SotaA this primer was only cured overnight at room temperature before infusion of the top layer, while the SotaB samples were also post-cured for 8 hours at 60°C.

Two sample types with the Crestomer adhesive were tested: one without a primer on the steel surface (VE-Cresto) and one with the Jotun primer applied on the steel (VE-CrestoJotun).

Stage 1: Initial peel strength tests on composite-steel joints

Peel tests were performed on non-aged specimens to determine the initial peel strength. A second objective of this stage was to find out which surface treatments were expected to perform well after aging by applying the “wet peel test” method as described by Kinloch (ref. [4]). In this method, the peel test is stopped after peeling a length of some centimeters. Then some water with 0.5% of detergent is applied at the crack tip and after a short time the test is continued. In the case of unstable adhesion and a poor water stability of the adhesion forces, an interfacial failure will be initiated and the peel strength will drop rapidly. According to Kinloch, there is a direct connection between the behavior of a joint in the wet peel test and the aging behavior in a natural humid climate. However, most specimens already demonstrated an interfacial failure before applying the water and no drop in peel strength could be observed.

Stage 2: Peel strength tests on composite-steel joints after aging

The performance after aging was also tested on a selected number of surface treatments. Both non-coated and coated specimens of each surface treatment were tested. The applied aging cycle was based on the recommended cycle in ASTM D1183 (ref. [5]). In this standard aging cycles in terms of conditions (temperature, humidity, immersion) and durations are given for several application conditions, among which are exterior parts for marine environments. This cycle was applied on the test specimens, with one amendment: the minimum temperature was raised from -57°C to -40°C due to limitations of the testing facilities. The applied aging cycle is shown in table 5.

Period [hrs]	Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	Relative humidity [%]
48	71	7
48	RT	Immersed in substitute ocean water
8	-40	-
64	RT	Immersed in substitute ocean water

Table 5: Aging cycle

4.4. RESULTS

Stage 1 (figure 6a):

Looking at the results the difference between the samples with separate adhesive and the samples with the laminated joints is the most apparent. The primed samples perform slightly better than the non-primed samples. Remarkable is the poor strength of the SotaA samples; the performance is even worse than the non-primed samples (VE-0 and VE-UV). No significant difference was found between the VE-0 baseline samples and the samples that underwent an additional UV-Ozone cleaning step.

Failure of the VE-0, VE-UV and VE-SotaA

samples occurred between the steel and composite resin interface (see also figure 4). Almost no resin is visible on the steel surface after the test. Failure of the SotaB samples was of a different kind: a significant amount of resin (and also some fibers) was left on the steel surface. This could be expected as the interface between the primed resin and the composite would be weaker than for the SotaA samples. All primed laminated joints failed within the primer layer: after testing primer was present on both the steel and the composite surfaces. Failure of both Crestomer samples occurred between the adhesive and the composite. A large amount of fibers was left in the adhesive after the tests.

Stage 2 (figure 6b):

After aging the ‘macro’-differences between the joints are the same as before aging: the Crestomer joints have by far the highest peel strengths, SotaA is the weakest and the primed samples are in the middle.

Figure 6a: Results stage 1 (non-aged)

For all samples the strength of the aged samples is equal to or higher than the strength of the non-aged samples. The assumed negative influence of the alternating temperatures and ocean water apparently has less influence than a positive post-cure like behavior during the 70°C-aging step. The coated samples give the highest strengths. Special attention must be paid to the Crestomer joints. The adhesive of the coated samples demonstrated a very high toughness. This caused troubles during the tests as no crack was initiated and the sample slipped in the grip of the climbing drum. For the non-coated samples (both aged and non-aged) cracks were initiated in the adhesive at the beginning of the tests, resulting in failure between the composite and the adhesive. No good tests have been achieved for the coated Crestomer joints without primer. The drop in peel strength for the coated Crestomer joints with Jotun primer is caused by a different failure: failure occurred in this case within the primer layer instead of at the adhesive-composite interface. Again, this is caused by the toughness of the adhesive, as no crack in the adhesive was initiated at the beginning of the interface.

Figure 6b: Results stage 1 and 2 (non-aged and aged)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Composite-composite joints:

- The resin-matrix interface was the weakest link in most cases instead of the secondary bonding.
- Secondary bonding is (therefore) not improved by the standard surface treatments (sanding, cleaning) after removal of the peel ply of the base panel.
- The state of cure of the base panel has an influence on the secondary bond; the best bond is achieved after partly curing of the base panel.
- The type of peel ply used during the infusion of the base laminate has a large influence on the bonding. Peel plies with release coating should be avoided.
- The type of resin has a large influence on the bonding strength.

Composite-steel joints:

- Joints with the Crestomer adhesive are much stronger than the laminated joints.
- Using the composite resin as primer does not have a significant effect on the bonding strength, but the use of suitable dedicated primers improves the joint.
- The applied aging cycle does not result in a decrease of bonding strength. Actually the strength increases due to a post-cure effect.
- The Crestomer adhesive retains a higher toughness after aging when a coating is applied.

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